

Extending the Moran scatterplot by indications of critical values and p -values: introducing the Moran seismogram and the drop plot

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Summary

The Moran scatterplot is a useful tool for exploring the spatial structure of datasets. The diagram plots spatial lags, that is, averaged spatial neighbourhoods, against their corresponding local attribute values. In this way, differently characterised autocorrelation sectors and structural breaks can be identified. However, the Moran scatterplot does not provide easily identifiable indications of possible spatial weight misspecification and p values. Both are important information when exploring possible spatial structures. In this short paper, so-called Moran seismograms and Moran drop plots are introduced, which complement the Moran scatterplot and visualise both types of information mentioned.

KEYWORDS: Moran scatterplot, Moran's I , spatial autocorrelation, exploratory spatial data analysis, spatial analysis.

1 Introduction

The Moran scatterplot has become an established graphical tool for exploring spatial structure. It plots spatial lags against the site-specific observations (Anselin, 1996) and allows both global (slope of a trendline) and local Moran's I (point positions categorised in four quadrants) to be visualised in one diagram, as well as the results of local Moran's I to be classified into hotspots, coldspots, and spatial outliers. Because Moran's I is a LISA statistic (Anselin, 1995), the scatterplot further enables diagnostics of the validity of the global measure by revealing, among other things, structural breaks and pockets of autocorrelation in different parts of the attribute value range. These diagnostic features, combined with its conceptual simplicity, have likely helped establishing the Moran scatterplot, which is now often reported alongside numerical results. In this paper, I put forward two ideas complementing the scatterplot: the Moran seismogram for diagnosing potential spatial weights misspecification, and the Moran drop plot for visualising p values.

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2 Literature review

Research on the Moran scatterplot beyond its applications (e.g., Lemmerz et al., 2023; Westerholt, 2021; Steiger et al., 2015) and implementations (e.g., PySAL Developers, 2017; Bivand and Wong, 2018; SAS Institute, 2019; Bivand, 2023) remains limited, but several variants and extensions have been proposed. Luc Anselin has contributed several variants of the Moran scatterplot through the GeoDa software ecosystem (see Anselin et al., 2022), including (Anselin, 2019a): a bivariate version plotting attribute values against the spatial lags of another variable, based on Anselin et al. (2002); a version accounting for differing base populations in rates, as proposed by Assunção and Reis (1999); a smoothed LOWESS trend line; a differential scatterplot accounting for fixed effects at geographic locations between two time steps; and a Moran scatterplot matrix arranging scatterplots for different time points. The latter temporal sequence of scatterplots is proposed by Ahn et al. (2009) for aggregation into sequences of allocated quadrant labels (e.g., ‘high-high’ or ‘low-low’), for which they present a similarity detection method based on the outlined temporal sequences. Rohde et al. (2015) complemented the latter by an improved method. Another approach to detecting temporal changes in the Moran scatterplot was presented by Rey et al. (2011), who propose to visualise translation vectors in the plot and then draw inferences about the observed pattern of change. This approach was complemented by a local version by Fiaschi et al. (2015). Some authors have addressed known shortcomings of the Moran scatterplot. Anselin (2019b) discusses a solution to label only those points as high-high or low-low that are truly numerically high or low by proposing a quantile-based autocorrelation approach. Another difficulty is that without interactive linked windows or similar approaches, the Moran scatterplot does not readily map actual geographic locations. Negreiros et al. (2010) therefore propose a so-called Moran location scatterplot replicating entire maps in all four quadrants in conjunction with appropriate significance signatures. They further propose a Moran variance scatterplot allowing to visualise different types of uncertainty regions.

3 Complementing the Moran scatterplot

This paper presents two ideas for enhancing the interpretability of the Moran scatterplot: the Moran seismogram that allows to visually diagnose potential issues with local spatial weights, and the Moran drop plot providing indications of p values. Both require determining the scatterplot positions of the critical values, beyond which standardised Moran’s I values Z_{I_i} would be flagged as significant. We have the observed attribute values (x-coordinates) at hand but need to determine the respective hypothetical spatial lags (y-coordinates). Since the inference procedures associated with local Moran’s I are typically two-sided, two such lags need to be calculated for the lower and upper tail, respectively. By rearranging the equation for standardised local Moran’s I , the spatial lags b_i required to obtain standardised critical values C_i can be determined as

$$b_i | x_i = \frac{s^2 \left(C_i \cdot \sqrt{\text{Var}[I_i]} + \text{E}[I_i] \right)}{(x_i - \bar{x})}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{x} and s^2 are the sample mean and variance of the attribute values x_i , and $\text{E}[\cdot]$ and $\text{Var}[\cdot]$ denote the expectation and variance operators. The hypothetical lags obtained in this way depend

Figure 1: Distribution of income in Greater Recife (Brazilian Portuguese: *Metropolitano de Recife*), Pernambuco, Brazil. Income values are given in Brazilian reais (R\$).

on the local spatial weights and are conditional on the attribute values x_i . To obtain the spatial lags sought, C_i can be substituted by any critical value. Assuming that local Moran’s I z-scores are approximately standard normal, we can substitute, for example, C_i with ± 2.58 (for $\alpha = 0.01$) or ± 1.96 ($\alpha = 0.05$). From the b_i values we can construct the seismogram and the drop plot, which are introduced below and are illustrated using the 2010 Census income variable for the Recife metropolitan area, Brazil (IBGE, 2011), mapped in Figure 1.

3.1 Moran seismogram

The proposed Moran seismogram is inspired by the idea of a seismogram for recording earthquakes. The diagram connects all scatterplot coordinates of the local critical values, separately for above- and below-average spatial lags. The resulting plot visualises the interplay between location-measured attribute values and local spatial configuration over the course of the attribute value range. Since the plot is ordered by attribute values through the x-axis, one would expect random fluctuation in a spatial configuration without imbalances in the map and without strong trends or outliers – comparable to the recording of a helicorder¹ when there is no earthquake or other kind of shaking. If, however, the variable of interest shows suspicious behaviour in parts of its spectrum, trends can be identified in the graph. Similarly, strong deflections indicate suspicious spatial units and local weights configurations that may be diagnosed in detail. The outlined fluctuations are subject to randomness through the range of possible hypothesised spatial lags b_i conditional on the observed values. However, the determination of such local distributions depends on the type of the null hypotheses and local inferences (see Sauer et al., 2022). Discerning notable spikes from random fluctuation thus requires a thorough investigation but is beyond the scope of this short paper. Figure 2 shows two Moran seismograms for the Recife income data obtained using normalised binary contiguity-based weights. In Figure 2b, a series of spikes can be seen, all associated with spatial units with low connectivity, such as along the periphery of the map or in unfortunate local configurations. The visualisation in Figure 2a is more uniform and only shows a few spikes in the third quadrant. The connectivity-related effects outlined are supported further by Figure 3, which indicates that the seismograms help illustrate a well-known problem with the weighting schemes used, namely that the W -coding gives too much weight to loosely connected units (Westerholt, 2022, p. 46 *f.*). The Moran seismogram is a complementary instrument to the Moran scatterplot, but it is also faced with some challenges. Line signatures could be misunderstood as relating actual observations, whereas they only facilitate indicating the location of unobserved critical values similar to how a trend line hints at correlation by its slope. Also, the shape of the line signature is influenced by differing numbers of points in the scatterplot (e.g., in the right tails in Figures 2a and b). This could be remedied by line discontinuities or varying colour saturation, strategies that are left for follow-up research.

3.2 Moran drop plot

One well-known shortcoming of the Moran scatterplot is that the plot does not provide information about p values. The Moran scatterplot indirectly encodes effect size (distance from trend line),

¹Helicorders are drum recorders that record the seismic information received by seismometers on paper.

(a) Moran seismogram for $\alpha = 0.01$ and binary spatial contiguity weights with C-normalisation.

(b) Moran seismogram for $\alpha = 0.01$ and binary spatial contiguity weights with W-normalisation.

Figure 2: Moran seismograms superimposed on Moran scatterplots. Red/blue lines connect the attribute–spatial lag tuples of critical values of positively/negatively autocorrelated observations.

(a) Binary spatial contiguity weights with C-normalisation; $C_i = \pm 2.58$

(b) Binary spatial contiguity weights with W-normalisation; $C_i = \pm 2.58$

Figure 3: The calculated critical Moran's I values b_i plotted against their local neighbourhood sizes.

(a) Moran drop plot for $\alpha = 0.01$ and binary spatial contiguity weights with C-normalisation

(b) Moran drop plot for $\alpha = 0.01$ and binary spatial contiguity weights with W-normalisation

Figure 4: Moran drop plots on top of Moran scatterplots. Drop lines show the distances of significant values (points) from their critical values for positive (red) and negative (blue) autocorrelation.

but not the confidence with which to conclude whether the effect observed might be more than just a mere random result. The proposed Moran drop plot addresses this shortcoming by not only visualising the significant units by highlighted points, but also showing their distances from the scatterplot coordinates of the associated critical values. The resulting lines literally ‘drop down’ (or ‘flow upwards’, if they are below the x-axis) and give an indication of the likelihood of the local Moran’s I results to be systematic and not random. In addition, the drop plot also mitigates the common misconception that the p values relate to the trend line. The latter describes global Moran’s I , but does not say much about individual local autocorrelations, as can be seen from the long drops appearing across the x-axis and irrespective of the trend line. The examples shown in Figure 4 illustrate drop plots for significant spatial units. The expected behaviour of this plot under spatial randomness is the observation of some drops both upwards and downwards, only a few of which would have large magnitudes. The results in both Figures 4a and b deviate from this and confirm the strong and clearly significant spatial autocorrelation of the income variable. They also show that particularly high incomes are strongly clustered, which can be confirmed by the map in Figure 1. There are only a few spatial outliers (highlighted in blue) located at the edges of the high-income clusters, illustrating the socio-economic segregation of Greater Recife. In addition to the variant shown in Figure 4 and explained up to this point, a second perspective adapted to non-significant points is also possible, which then shows how ‘random’ local results are (not illustrated). The drop plot supplements the Moran scatterplot with a straightforward possibility of interpreting graphically indications of p values alongside local spatial autocorrelation and thus effect size. Collectively, all lines considered together provide the analyst with a summary of how likely or unlikely it generally is that the significant results would be obtained under random conditions, which can be seen as a graphical decomposition of the p -value of global Moran’s I in a LISA sense.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, two types of diagrams were presented to complement the Moran scatterplot for exploratory data analysis. The proposed Moran seismogram allows investigating potential misspecification of spatial weights by connecting the positions of critical values in the Moran scatterplot. Moreover, Moran drop plots are proposed to plot p values of local Moran’s I on the attribute value spectrum, which is an additional means to diagnose interesting pockets of spatial structure besides geographically mapping p values. While the proposed plots are helpful additions to the exploratory toolbox, a systematic understanding of whether and how they are able to convey the intended messages to different user groups remains unknown. This also largely applies to the traditional Moran scatterplot. Future research should therefore focus on user studies for a more systematic understanding of corresponding visual devices.

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Biography

René Westerholt is tenure-track Juniorprofessor and head of the Spatial Modelling Lab at TU Dortmund University (Germany). His research interests are focused on geographic information science (especially in urban analytics and formalising space and place) and spatial statistics (focusing on exploratory spatial data analysis methods).

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